

THE ROLE OF COMPETITIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH'S CREATIVE SKILLS

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of pageants in the development of creative abilities of young people are analyzed on the example of pageants organized on a large scale in Uzbekistan, and the specific characteristics and consequences of pageants as a social event affecting the social development of society members are stated.*

Keywords: *audition, education, youth, culture, thinking, personality, cultural necessity, social life, spiritual and educational activity.*

The task of building a democratic legal state and civil society in Uzbekistan to create a new generation of morally mature and competent specialists, and changes in society are related to the new way of thinking of young people, changing their worldview, increasing their political consciousness and culture. Life itself and the experience of the past years demand the elimination of serious deficiencies in ensuring comprehensive development of regions and fundamental changes in infrastructure activities. [1.-B. 14.] Indeed, the development of effective methods and tools is an important issue in ensuring social development. In particular, a new approach to meeting the cultural needs of the population is needed.

Society is such a unique structure that it is impossible that every process that takes place in it does not effect the social life of its members. Based on these features, cultural and educational events serve to increase the consciousness of the members of the society, assimilation of the laws and values of the society.

The development of the society are related to the inner spiritual-moral, political world, life imagination, actions and goals of young people and feelings of self-sacrifice. After all, pageants and festivals are the means of forming these feelings. The essence of this way is to build a society of free citizens based on market relations, to create decent living conditions for our people. To achieve this, first of all, it is necessary to increase the social activity of society members. Spiritual and educational activities have a special place in this.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the organization of the spiritual and educational gesture, first of all, among the younger members of the society, that are, children, youth, will undoubtedly ensure the effectiveness of today's reforms in the field of education and training. In this regard, the role of pageants and festivals held among children and young people are very important. At this point, let's analyze the social phenomena that occur in children and young people using the means of examination. First, the content of the exam ensures that children and young people acquire certain knowledge and skills.

Secondly, the atmosphere of competition among the participants of the competition makes students more competitive, increases the feeling of not bowing before the tests, and brings out the ability of ideological struggle.

Thirdly, based on the selection criteria, the participant will have a vital position. Because in that period it embodies a certain life level of the person in his life and social life. It is here that ideas about the point of life are formed. He begins to understand his role.

Fourthly, organizational and leadership skills are formed in young students, and personal responsibility begins to take the place of childhood aspects. Fifthly, children and young people forget all their social problems during the exam process and consider the conditions of the exam as a rule of life and prepare for it. In this process, their thinking and memory are cleared. It gets rid of unnecessary information and memory is strengthened.

Sixth, any examination - competition is organized on the basis of certain approved regulations and the participants are required to follow its rules. This allow students to organize their lives in society on the basis of laws and regulations. The student also serves the formation of the legal culture of young people.

It creates important conditions for the social and emotional development of students, as well as expanding their educational opportunities. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of pageants and festivals are held for this purpose.

"The art of literary words have always been an expression of the people's heart, a herald of truth and justice. In particular, in the years of independence, the development of poetry, which is an extremely important and integral part of our spirituality, the appreciation of the noble work of our poets, and the appropriate encouragement of our poets, are giving their character, in terms of the scope of our fiction literature. The fact that it is becoming more colorful, both in terms of genres, and that new names are appearing in the field of poetry will definitely make our readers please" [2.-B.176.] - says I.A.Karimov.

Students of higher educational institutions participate with their creative works in the national competition "Young Readers". The participation of students and young people in the competition are ensured and coordinated by vice-rectors for spiritual and educational affairs of higher educational institutions. The main goal of the contest is to promote among students and young people the role and importance of artistic works in our lives, to raise our young people to be healthy and well-rounded in all aspects, to create conditions for them to use books, to be independent and free-thinking. It consists of all-round support for young people. The tasks of the contests are as follows:

- instilling in the minds of young people the role and importance of artistic works in the formation and strengthening of high spirituality in our society, as well as the large-scale work carried out in the years of independence to promote reading, create and support artistic works in our country;

- to familiarize students with the newly created works of art, to read and analyze the book, and to form their skills and abilities to express their independent opinion;

- to further increase the effectiveness of the promotion of reading among young people;

- to further enrich students' imaginations about the importance of the book in educating the young generation to become mature, highly spiritual, intellectually capable people who are loyal to their parents and Motherland;

- to convey the creative works of talented and gifted students to the general public, to determine the spiritual needs of readers and to encourage them;

- to further increase the activity of young people in spiritual, educational and creative activities through book promotion.

"If we want to glorify our Uzbekistan to the world, glorify its ancient history and bright future, and keep it forever in the memory of generations, first of all we need to educate great

writers, great poets, great creators"[3.-B.38.]. In fact, events dedicated to read such books allow to discover and develop creators.

Competitions and festivals have a significant role in the formation of legal culture among students. It is called "Law Scholars", "Do you know the law?" can also be seen in auditions.

Number of competitions and festivals aimed at improving the legal culture of young people in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Among them, the competition "Do you know the law?" is of particular importance.

The purpose of the examination is increasing the legal knowledge, consciousness and culture of the students of educational institutions, to educate them in the spirit of respect for the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents, to develop the ability of free thinking and speech culture of young people, to further their active citizenship position. It is held for the purpose of strengthening, identifying and motivating talented students.

It is attended by groups consisting of students of non-legal secondary vocational education institutions located in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city. Organizing and conducting the competition are entrusted to the organizational working group consisting of representatives of responsible organizers.

Formation of groups of educational institutions participating in the competition is carried out by appropriate educational institutions and other responsible organizations in the order of 8 people. The groups are made up of only students of the educational institution participating in the competition.

There are such families in the society, which are often dominated by the ideals of filial piety. In these families, everything is subordinated to one thing, that is, it is aimed at accumulating wealth and achieving superiority in material and household terms. The work of adult family members and parents in an enterprise, institution, organization is a means of achieving this goal, and any work is measured by the amount of salary.

The violence, tyranny of the head of the family, blind and unconditional obedience to him, worshipping him, striving to destroy the activity of weak family members, etc. will prevail. Cases of going beyond the ideal of morality and religious beliefs (reading books, participating in social activities) are considered to be a waste of time. Therefore, boys and girls who are of little benefit to society may grow up from families belonging to low social status [4.-B.76.]. It is an important issue to involve the children of such families in auditions.

Competitions and festivals organized among children and youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan are characterized by the following:

It guarantees the increase of social activity of young members of the society;

Youth and children develop interest in a certain profession;

Mobilizes youth and children in creative activities;

It helps children and young people to take life positions;

It serves as a school of experience to cultivate the will to overcome various difficulties by creating a sense of struggle for life in young people and children.

In conclusion, it should be said that pageants and festivals are integral part of the social life and express the way of life of people in a unique way. In particular, it helps young people to increase their confidence in the future.

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